

MAIN APPROACHES OF THE READER-RESPONSE THEORY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12644128>

Abstract: This article discusses peculiarities of the reader response theory within the main approaches of it. The literary text, reader and interpreting the text being the key notions of the theory are studied within the approaches mentioned in the article.

Key words: Reader-response criticism, Transactional approach, Historical context, Affective stylistics, Psychological approach, Subjective approach, Social approach, Textual approach.

One of the main critical schools in modern culture and literary studies, reader-response criticism, has contributed significantly to the way we read the texts. Often called the criticism of consciousness, it originated with the phenomenological approach of renowned philosopher Edmund Husserl in the 20th century. In line with this, it was also modified by the use of hermeneutics in Hans-Georg Gadamer's conceptual framework¹. Late in the 1970s and early in the 1980s, reader-oriented techniques gained popularity. To a large degree, this strategy was established by individuals such as Gerald Prince, Louise M. Rosenblatt, Norman Holland, Stanley Fish, and David Bleich. This form of critique was also greatly aided in its growth by the writings of the Constance school critics, such as Wolfgang Iser and Hans Robert Jauss. As a result, the reader-response approach to reading the texts was given access to a new toolbox of extremely technical terms, including the Implied/Actual Reader dichotomy, Concretization, Negation, Assimilation, Creation, and Horizons of Expectation. Within the context of current figures' new theoretical frameworks, reader-response criticism has been extensively studied over the past few decades. There are multiple approaches to classify reader-response theory: Louise Rosenblatt and Wolfgang Iser's transactional approach, Hans Robert Jauss's preferred historical context, The affective stylistics by Stanley Fish, Norman Holland used a psychological approach, Subjective method in David Bleich's works, Stanley Fish's mature works employ a social approach, while Gerald Prince's work employs a textual approach.

Transactional|| approach. A Transactional reader-response critic, Louise M. Rosenblatt asserts that both the reader and the text must work together to produce meaning². They share or take part in a transactional experience. The text serves as a catalyst for the reader to recall a variety of prior encounters, ideas, and thoughts from both prior reading experiences and our daily lives. Upon reading the text, readers bring with them their unique personalities, recollections of past events, current problems, unique physical conditions, and their entire individuality. But the text also acts as a blueprint, picking, reducing, and prioritizing thoughts that best fit the book's framework in order to mold the reader's experiences in its image. She

¹ Guerin, Wilfred L. et al. *A Handbook of Critical Approaches to Literature*. Fifth edition. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2015.

² Rosenblatt, Louise. *The Reader, The Text, The Poem: The Transactional Theory of the Literary Work*. Carbondale: Southern Illinois University Press, 1978.

refers to the new work that the reader and the text create together as a poem. This is the result of their transactional interaction. The two main divisions of reading, according to Rosenblatt, are: Engaging in efferent reading occurs when we read for information. Conversely, when we interact with the text, we read in an artistic way. A conversation between the reader and the text is what happens when we read beautifully. Between an efferent and an aesthetic mode of reading, a reader may alternate between them during the reading process.

Historical approach. Hans Robert Jauss, an important German exponent of 'reception theory,' gave a historical dimension to reader-oriented criticism. Literary works are not standalone objects that present the same perspective to every reader at every time, according to Jauss in *Toward an Aesthetic Reception*. The monument doesn't convey its timeless core in a monological manner³. He goes on to say that when understanding a text, one must take its social history into account. Furthermore, Jauss employs the phrase "horizons of expectation" to delineate the standards by which readers evaluate literary works within a specific age. He contends that since every historical era creates its own expectations, the text's meaning can never be definitive or universal. Because a text's meaning might vary depending on the historical context, there is no one right way to interpret it.

Affective stylistics approach. An American exponent of reader-response criticism, Stanley fish examined the differences between the affective and reception aesthetics. He is one of the practitioners of affective stylistics⁴. Rather than being an object that exists in place, they contend that a literary text is an event that occurs in time and comes into being as it is read. A thorough analysis of the text is conducted to determine how (stylistically) and (affectively) the reader is affected while reading it. Fish believes that because the text is made up of the effects it generates, which happen inside the reader, it cannot be viewed as an objective, autonomous entity with a fixed meaning that exists independently of readers. The structure that Fish describes in his analysis of a book is the structure that emerges from the reader's response as it happens in real time. Affective stylistics is a cognitive study of how particular brain processes create

Psychological approach. A psychological reader-response critic, Holland's method is transactive in the sense that reading involves a transaction between the reader and the text. When we read literature, we project our identity theme, or variations of it, on to the text⁵. The world we envision in our minds is unintentionally recreated in the text. We project our needs, wants, defenses, and fears onto the text, which results in our interpretations. The reader's psyche is thereby revealed through the psychological process of interpretation. Holland claims that the process of interpretation has three phases, or modes: The text triggers defense mode, which increases our psychological barriers. We decipher the material in a way that

³ Jauss, Hans Robert. *Toward an Aesthetic of Reception*. Minneapolis: The University of Minnesota Press, 1982.

⁴ Fish, Stanley. —Faulty Perspectives. In *Modern Criticism and Theory: A Reader*. Ed. David Lodge and Nigel Wood. New York: Longman, 2011. P 287-116.

⁵ Holland, Norman. —Unity Identity Text Self. In *PMLA (6975): 869-822*. Rpt. In *Reader Response Criticism: From Formalist to Post-Structuralism*. Ed. Jane P. Tompkins. Baltimore: The Johns Hopkins University Press, 1981. P 118-99.

calms those defenses in the dream mode, satisfying our need to be shielded from dangers that could upset our psychological balance.

Lastly, we turn the first two steps into an abstract interpretation in the transformation mode in order to achieve the psychological fulfillment we seek (without admitting to ourselves the guilt-inducing fantasies and anxiety-inducing defenses that underpin our interpretation of the text). Holland suggests DEFT as the most appropriate acronym to represent the defense-fantasy-transformation paradigm of the literary experience.

Subjective approach. An American subjective reader-response critic, David Bleich argues that the text is created by readers' responses, in the sense that there is no literary text beyond the meanings created by readers' interpretation; the text the critic analyzes is not the literary work but the written responses of readers⁶. The sensation, connections, and recollections that arise from our subjective response to the written words on a page are what he refers to as symbolization in reading. As we read, a mental universe of concepts is created by our perception and identification of the reading experience. As a result, when we understand the text, what we are really understanding is the meaning of our own symbolization or the meaning of the conceptual experience we developed in reaction to the text. One can develop the meaning of the text through discussions and agreements. The group determines what constitutes a legitimate reading of the text.

Social approach. In *Interpreting the Variorum*|| Fish delineates that interpretive communities are made up of those who share interpretive strategies not for reading (in the conventional sense) but for writing texts, for constituting their properties and assigning their intentions⁷. Put differently, these reading techniques are in place before the act of reading and hence influence the content that is read. A readership that uses similar interpretive techniques is therefore referred to as an interpretive community. Interpretive methods are learnt rather than innate, according to Fish, who also claims that "interpretive communities grow and decline, and individuals move from one to another." Since the reader's reading community is where a piece acquires its meaning, social media plays a big part in Fish's more mature works.

Textual approach. Prince states that by observing and analyzing various signs in the text, such as pronoun reference, direct address, gender, race, social class references, and writing styles, it is possible to identify the narratee⁸. The study of stories with an emphasis on narrator, voice, style, and other aspects of storytelling is known as narrative analysis. The term "narratee" refers to the individual the narrator is speaking to. The storyteller is created by the story itself. Three distinct types of narratees exist: The Real reader, who is the person who is actually reading the book; The Virtual reader, who is the reader to whom the writer feels they are writing; and The Ideal reader, who is the person who knows every word and structure of the text both explicitly and implicitly. Prince belongs to the reader-oriented school of criticism even if his method is based on textual analysis because of his consideration for the reader.

⁶ Bleich, David. *Subjective Criticism*.|| Baltimore: The Johns Hopkins University Press, 1978.

⁷ Fish, Stanley. —*Faulty Perspectives*.|| *Modern Criticism and Theory: A Reader*. Ed. David Lodge and Nigel Wood. New York: Longman, 2011. P 287-116.

⁸ Gerald, Prince. *A Dictionary of Narratology*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1987. ---. *Narrative as Theme: Studies in French Fiction*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1992.

Reading and the reader's subjective interpretation of the texts' meaning are closely related processes. For the reader, meaning is produced through the confusion between the active reader and the active text. Interpretations should not be set and immutable because the meaning is always delayed⁹. Hence, the reader's pivotal function remains a primary factor contributing significantly to the relevance of the reading experience. For reading texts in modern literary and cultural studies, the reader-response technique offers a highly significant approach. With the introduction of new specialized language by prominent players in this manner of inquiry, reader-oriented criticism has completely evolved as a critical approach. Reader-response theory could be categorized into several modes including transactional, historical context, affective stylistics, psychological, subjective, social, and textual approaches.

To sum up, by examining the mechanism of reading in terms of the primary ideas of the methods of reception theory, the process might be further developed. As a result, when analyzing the reading process, it is important to regularly take into account the reader's vital position in the reading process as well as their value in making meaning.

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⁹ Махмудова Н.А. Жанр роман воспитания: проблемы методологии анализа //Ўзбекистонда хорижий тиллар. — 2021. — № 1 (36). — С. 242-256.